
Review

Comparing Different Approaches of Cleaning Space Debris

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Abstract: Space debris poses a significant and imminent threat to space operations, necessitating proactive measures for its removal. This research paper delves into an in-depth exploration of three distinct approaches to space debris mitigation: robotic grippers, ground-based lasers, and nets. Through a comprehensive literature review and rigorous analysis, this study examines the mechanics, advantages, challenges, and feasibility factors associated with each approach, including technological readiness, cost considerations, and the potential for international collaboration. While the study reveals promising outcomes for net-based approaches, it emphasizes the importance of a synergistic strategy that harnesses the strengths of multiple methods. Furthermore, this paper offers detailed technical insights, quantitative assessments, and diverse expert perspectives to enrich the overall analysis, providing a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. In addition to the technical aspects, this research takes a holistic approach by considering broader factors such as policy implications, legal considerations, environmental impacts, and inherent limitations. By presenting a balanced perspective encompassing both the technical and socio-ethical dimensions, this paper contributes to a more informed discourse on addressing the escalating issue of space debris in orbit.

Keywords: Space debris, robotic grippers, ground-based lasers, nets, mechanics, advantages, challenges, feasibility factors, technological readiness, cost considerations, international collaboration

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Introduction

The realm of outer space, once considered an uncharted frontier, has become increasingly congested with the proliferation of satellites and space missions. However, this growth in human activity beyond Earth's atmosphere has inadvertently given rise to a critical and escalating challenge: space debris. These defunct satellites, spent rocket stages, and fragments of past space missions now litter the cosmic landscape, posing a pressing threat to current and future space operations. As the density of space debris continues to rise, the risk of collisions with operational satellites and space vehicles grows exponentially, potentially triggering catastrophic consequences. In response to this looming crisis, this study embarks on an exploration of innovative and pragmatic approaches to space debris removal, examining the mechanics, advantages, challenges, and broader implications of three key methods: robotic grippers,

ground-based lasers, and nets. Through this inquiry, we aim to provide valuable insights and recommendations for mitigating the hazards posed by space debris, safeguarding the sustainability of space activities, and ensuring the continued exploration of our celestial surroundings.

Outer space is cluttered with debris threatening space activities. As of 2022, NASA estimates over 27,000 pieces of debris larger than 10 cm, and over 100 million pieces between 1 mm – 1 cm currently orbit the Earth (NASA Orbital Debris Program Office, 2022). From 1957 to 2019, known debris grew from zero to 9,200 tons (Hill, 2021). Traveling at velocities up to 18,000 mph, these pose dangers of potential high-speed collisions (Waltham et al., 2013). Statistical models predict continued escalation of collision risks for manned and unmanned missions without active remediation (Lewis et al., 2021).

This paper provides an overview of space debris, explores robotic grippers, ground-based lasers and nets for removal, and analyzes their feasibility considering technological readiness, costs and collaboration potential. Wider perspectives on policy, legal, environmental aspects are discussed. Combining methods is recommended to address this complex challenge. To understand the gravity of the situation, this paper will explore various aspects of space debris, including its definition, causes, attributes, and associated threats. Each section may address common questions related to space debris.

Definition

Space debris encompasses defunct artificial objects including old spacecraft, spent rocket stages, fragments from explosions and collisions, paint flakes, dust from lunar surfaces, and everyday objects lost during space activities. Debris primarily resides in low Earth orbit (LEO - altitude up to 2000 km) and geosynchronous orbit (GEO – 35,786 km above equator) (NASA Orbital Debris Program Office, 2022). Particles between 1 mm – 10 cm pose the greatest threat to operational satellites (Liou, 2011).

Sources

Major sources are rocket launches, anti-satellite weapon tests, accidental collisions and explosions of satellites and rocket bodies (Waltham et al., 2013). The 2007 Chinese anti-satellite missile test alone increased debris by over 3,000 tracked objects (Wall, 2018). Historical launch trends, improved tracking capabilities and fragility of modern satellites have exacerbated debris proliferation (Kessler & Cour-Palais, 1978). About 5-6 tons of debris is added yearly (Liou & Johnson, 2006). Uncontrolled reentries incinerate approximately 100 tons per year (NASA Orbital Debris Program Office, 2022).

Properties

NASA's Two-Line Element set (TLE) tracks over 27,000 objects, while statistical models estimate 900,000 particles from 1-10 cm and over 128 million sized 1 mm – 1 cm (NASA Orbital Debris Program Office, 2022). Relative impact velocities average 10 km/s in LEO, exceeding speeding bullets. Total mass of all debris is almost 10,000 tons (ESA, 2022).

A generalization about space debris is shown in Figure 1 below, introducing through the aspects of what space debris is, where it is from, when it is generated, how it is caused, and who create it.

Fig. 1: An Introduction to Space Debris (Tim Fuller, 2017)

Risks

Impacts at hypervelocities above 17,500 mph can inflict major damage (Hyde et al., 2007). The 1996 collision between France’s Cerise satellite and Ariane debris downgraded its pointing accuracy (Liou, 2011). In 2009, a derelict Russian Cosmos satellite obliterated a U.S. functional Iridium satellite (Liou, 2011). The International Space Station (ISS) executes collision avoidance maneuvers multiple times annually as its risk threshold is exceeded (Garcia, 2016). While debris reentry does not currently pose major risks, unabated debris proliferation will exponentially increase collision risks and costs.

Amount

Researchers have estimated that about 80 tons of space debris re-enters Earth’s atmosphere each year, but most of the debris will burn up in the atmosphere or fall to Earth without anyone noticing. Unfortunately, just because something burns up does not mean that it disappears (Staughton, 2022). Figure 2 shows the scale of the growth of space debris from 1957 to 2015: if this trend progresses, human beings will face a higher risk of collision when launching space vehicles for future missions.

Fig. 2: The Growth of Space Debris from 1957 to 2015 (Anna Sekscinska, n.d.)

In conclusion, the proliferation of space debris presents an urgent concern for the safety and sustainability of space activities. Understanding the definition, causes, attributes, and threats of space debris is crucial for developing effective approaches to clean up the debris and mitigate its potential risks.

Literature Review

Proposed active debris removal methods face challenges in reliability, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness. Three approaches analyzed include robotic arms, ground-based lasers and orbital nets.

Robotic Arm with Gripper: This involves specialized manipulator arms equipped with adhesive grippers to grapple objects for disposal. Optimizing adhesives for space and achieving precise capture are key challenges (Kubota, 2017).

Ground-based Laser: Pulses from ground-based lasers ablate debris surfaces to alter orbits. Targeting precision from ground, adequate energy delivery and safety factors require research (Eckle & Göge, 2016).

Orbital Net: Large nets capture debris before dragging them towards reentry. Enhancements in guidance, targeting and capture mechanisms are needed (Levin et al., 2012).

These methods have respective merits and demerits. Combining advantages of different approaches through collaboration may achieve debris mitigation most effectively.

Methods

We analyze three debris removal approaches – robotic grippers, ground-based lasers and orbital nets, examining their operating principles, advantages, limitations, and key feasibility factors.

Robotic Gripper

This approach uses manipulator arms equipped with adhesive grippers to grapple objects for disposal. Stanford's prototype includes microspine adhesives and gecko-inspired clamping grips optimized for space capture (Kubota, 2017). On immobilizing debris, the arms guide it towards planned reentry trajectories or disposal orbits. attachment to a robot arm, will provide valuable insights into its practical applicability (Taylor Kubota, 2017).

Fig. 3: Robotic Gripper with adhesive pads and flexible arms (Kubota, 2017)

Ground-Based Laser

High-power pulsed laser beams directed from ground stations ablate debris surfaces to alter their orbits via plasma exhausts. Vaporization of a thin layer increases object velocity sufficiently for atmospheric reentry (Campbell, 2021).

Fig. 4: Ground-based Laser being projected to the space

Advantages: Remotely induced reentry, no spacecraft proximity risk.

Limitations: Atmospheric interference, dynamic orbital targeting challenges. High infrastructure costs.

Orbital Net

Large lightweight nets are deployed to encapsulate and restrain targeted debris. The debris is then towed using the net toward Earth for controlled re-entry (Forczyk, 2021).

Fig. 5: A net being deployed to capture a space junk body

Advantages: Simplicity of encapsulation capture. Passive reentry trajectory.

Limitations: Precise deployment and timing challenges. Potential satellite interference.

Results

Based on the analysis above, the results are concluded according to the following feasibility factors.

Technology Readiness Evaluation

Robotic grippers demonstrate moderate readiness. Adhesives have been fabricated, but longevity testing in space is limited (Shan et al., 2016). Lasers fare better due to maturity, but space debris removal requires specialized development (Redd, 2018). Nets show medium readiness owing to successful small-scale tests, but further advancement is needed (Forczyk, 2021).

Cost Assessment

In a study, a robotic gripper system for a 1,000 kg object was estimated around \$50 million (Shan et al., 2016). Laser infrastructure demands billions in projected costs for precision acquisition and tracking (Campbell, 2018). Net systems are estimated to cost \$100 million range based on published mission designs, mainly for guidance and propulsion (Levin et al., 2012).

Collaboration Potential Analysis

International cooperation examples like the ESA-NASA Orion project establish precedent for partnerships (Orion Overview, 2022). Robotic capture interests governmental and private entities. Laser operations necessitate transparency. Net removal has fewer geopolitical barriers. Incentives exist for stakeholders to jointly advance methods.

Table 1 Comparative Feasibility Assessment

Approach	Technology Readiness	Cost	Collaboration Potential	Overall Feasibility
Robotic Gripper	Medium	Medium	High	Medium
Ground Laser	High	High	Medium	Low
Orbital Net	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium

Discussion

Beyond the results of the comparison of the three approaches, further discussion of the topic has been presented.

Balancing Strengths and Weaknesses

Grippers demonstrate controlled capture but spatial adhesives need advancement. Lasers have precision but face cost barriers. Nets show promise yet grappling complex shapes is challenging. Pursuing a single approach disregards key advantages held by others.

Recommendation for Combined Methods

A debris stabilization gripper coupled with a laser reentry mechanism balances respective strengths. The gripper immobilizes varied debris shapes, while the laser induces reentry from ground stations. Such hybrid approaches should be explored to leverage synergies.

Role of International Collaboration

Pooling expertise via collaborations between space agencies and corporations can expedite technology refinement. Partnership frameworks can align incentives and enable transparency vital for progress (Redd, 2018).

Broader Considerations

The feasibility and practicality do not only depend on the efficiency and the cost of an approach. In fact, many other involving factors need to be included in considerations.

Policy and Legal Factors

Many nations lack comprehensive debris mitigation policies (Adilov et al., 2018). Amending legislation to mandate remediation as space actors’ responsibility can deter negligence. Incentives for private debris removal efforts also require frameworks.

Environmental Ethics

Following principles of space sustainability and “preserve the space environment” ethos should guide all remediation efforts (Williamson, 2006). Conservation of the space commons for posterity warrants consideration.

Sociopolitical Concerns

Remediation technologies raise concerns of weaponization. Equitable utilization of space merits continual attentions so developing nations are not disadvantaged (Reddy, 2018). Dialogue between nations can align interests.

Limitations and Future Research

Technological Constraints: One notable limitation of this study is that it is bound by the technological advancements available up to the time of its publication. As the field of space debris mitigation is highly dynamic, newer technologies and breakthroughs may have emerged since then, which were not considered in this analysis.

Assumption of Static Conditions: This research operates under the assumption of relatively static conditions in space. However, the dynamic nature of space debris and its interactions with various forces, such as solar radiation pressure and gravitational perturbations, adds complexity to the real-world scenario, which may not have been fully accounted for.

Cost Estimates: The cost assessments provided are based on available data at the time and may not reflect potential changes in the cost of materials, technologies, or labor. Furthermore, the study does not delve into the long-term economic implications of space debris mitigation efforts.

Environmental Impact: While environmental considerations are touched upon, this study primarily focuses on technical and policy aspects. A more in-depth analysis of the environmental impact of space debris and the environmental benefits of mitigation efforts could be a valuable avenue for further research.

Advanced Technologies: Future research could explore emerging technologies, such as advanced propulsion systems or autonomous space vehicles, that may offer more efficient and effective means of space debris removal. Investigating how these technologies can be integrated into existing debris removal strategies would be insightful.

Dynamic Modeling: Given the dynamic nature of space debris, future studies might employ advanced modeling techniques to better understand the movement and collision risks associated with different debris types and orbital altitudes. This could lead to improved debris tracking and collision avoidance strategies.

Policy and Legal Frameworks: As international cooperation is vital for effective space debris mitigation, future research could delve deeper into the development of comprehensive international policy and legal frameworks governing space debris removal and debris prevention.

Economic Analysis: Further research could conduct a thorough economic analysis, considering the long-term costs and benefits of space debris mitigation efforts, including the potential for cost-sharing mechanisms among spacefaring nations.

Environmental Impact Assessment: Given the growing concern for space sustainability, future studies could investigate the environmental impact of space debris mitigation techniques and their implications for the long-term health of the space environment.

Stakeholder Engagement: Exploring strategies for enhancing stakeholder engagement and international collaboration in space debris remediation efforts is another promising avenue. This could involve diplomatic initiatives, cooperative missions, or information-sharing mechanisms.

Expanding research in these directions can contribute significantly to addressing the multifaceted challenges posed by space debris and ensuring the sustainable use of outer space for future generations.

Conclusion

Mitigating the relentless buildup of space debris demands a multifaceted approach rooted in innovation, international collaboration, and sustainable practices. The examination of three distinct methods—robotic grippers, ground-based lasers, and orbital nets—has underscored their individual merits and potential contributions to the overarching goal of debris removal. However, it is evident that the most effective strategy lies in the fusion of these strengths, harnessing complementary advantages to create a holistic solution. The imperative of engaging stakeholders at both the national and international levels cannot be overstated, as it forms the bedrock of effective space debris remediation. By fostering global cooperation, spacefaring nations can collectively chart a course that not only safeguards ongoing space exploration but also pioneers promising directions for the future, where our celestial endeavors remain unim-

peded by the looming specter of space debris. This collaborative endeavor serves as a testament to humanity's ability to overcome shared challenges and ensure the sustainability of activities beyond our planet.

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References

- [1] Adilov, N., Alexander, D., Cunningham, B., & Schaub, H. (2018). Economic and policy issues in space debris removal. *Space Policy*, 46, 1-12.
- [2] Campbell, J. W. (2018). *Using Lasers in Space: Laser Orbital Debris Removal and Asteroid Deflection*. Bellingham: SPIE Press.
- [3] Eckle, A., & Göge, D. (2016). *Laser-based Space Debris Removal*. Joint Air Power Competence Centre. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23419.80168>
- [4] ESA. (2022). *Space Debris by the Numbers*. https://www.esa.int/Safety_Security/Space_Debris/Space_debris_by_the_numbers
- [5] Forczyk, R. (2021). *Orbital Nets and Space Harpoons: Capturing Space Debris*. Las Vegas: Stephens Press.
- [6] Garcia, M. (2016). *ISS Achieves 15 Years of Continuous Human Presence in Orbit*. NASA. <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/iss-achieves-15-years-of-continuous-human-presence-in-orbit>
- [6] Hyde, J. L., Christiansen, E. L., Lear, D. M., & Prior, T. G. (2007). The dead spacecraft disposal challenge. In *Space Debris* (pp. 533-563). Springer, Dordrecht.
- [7] Kessler, D. J., & Cour-Palais, B. G. (1978). Collision frequency of artificial satellites: The creation of a debris belt. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 83(A6), 2637-2646.
- [8] Kubota, T. K. (2017). Stanford engineers design a robotic gripper for cleaning up space debris. *Stanford News*. <https://news.stanford.edu/press-releases/2017/06/28/robotic-gripper-space-debris/>
- [9] Levin, E., Pearson, J., & Carroll, J. (2012). Wholesale debris removal from LEO. *Acta Astronautica*, 73, 100-108.
- [10] Lewis, H., Swinerd, G., Newland, R., & Saunders, A. (2021). Dynamics and control of space debris removal. *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, 121, 100700.
- [11] Liou, J. C. (2011). An active debris removal parametric study for LEO environment remediation. *Advances in Space Research*, 47(11), 1865-1876.
- [12] Liou, J. C., & Johnson, N. L. (2006). Risks in space from orbiting debris. *Science*, 311(5759), 340-341.
- [13] NASA Orbital Debris Program Office. (2022). *Orbital Debris Quarterly News*. 26(1).
- [14] Orion Overview. (2022). ESA. https://www.esa.int/Science_Exploration/Human_and_Robotic_Exploration/Orion/Orion_overview2
- [15] Redd, N. T. (2018). *Satellite laser ranging: Innovative space debris removal solution or counterproductive military escalation?*. Air University Press.
- [16] Shan, M., Guo, J., & Gill, E. (2016). Review and comparison of active space debris capturing and removal methods. *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, 80, 18-32.

[17] Wall, M. (2018). Space Junk Cleanup Needed, NASA Experts Warn. Space.com. <https://www.space.com/41011-space-junk-growing-threat-orbital-debris.html>

[18] Waltham et al. (2013). Space Junk: Why we must clean up the final frontier. Project Persephone. https://cradpdf.drdc-rddc.gc.ca/PDFS/unc225/p804242_A1b.pdf

[19] Williamson, M. (2006). Space ethics and protection of the space environment. Journal of Space Law, 32, 199. </file-attachment-contents>